

Injection fluids based on humic acid-3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane complexes for immobilization of heavy metals

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The Arctic zone of the Russian Federation is subject to intense pollution by heavy metals (HM), primarily Ni, Cu and Pb, due to the activities of mining and metallurgical enterprises. High mobility of toxic metals creates risks for ecosystems and public health, which requires the development of effective and nature-like methods of immobilization. The objective of this research was preparation and characterization of new remedial agents based on polyelectrolyte complexes (PEC) of humic substances (HS) and 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) for in situ installation of permeable reaction barriers (PRB) capable of intercepting and immobilizing HM in the contaminated aquifers.

Field sampling and comprehensive analysis of soils in the Norilsk region (ICP-OES) was carried out to determine the content of total and mobile forms of heavy metals with a use of nitric acid and ammonium acetate buffer extraction, respectively. Humic acids (HA) and fulvic acids (FA) were isolated from peats and permafrost of the Arctic zone. Their structural and group composition was studied using elemental analysis and NMR ^{13}C . The kinetics and isotherms of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} sorption on native HA were studied. PECs with different stoichiometric ratios of APTES/HS were obtained. Their sorption kinetics and isotherms were studied on a model mineral carrier (silica gel). The efficiency of immobilized PECs under static and dynamic conditions for the sorption of Cu, Ni, and Pb was estimated.

It was found that the content of mobile forms of Ni and Cu in soils decreased exponentially with distance from the pollution source. A direct correlation was revealed between the content of mobile forms of HM and sulfur. The HA samples isolated from permafrost and peat demonstrated high sorption capacity with respect to Cu^{2+} (26–31 mg/g) and Ni^{2+} (14–19 mg/g). The sorption values dropped sharply at $\text{pH} < 4$. It was shown that APTES/HS PEC effectively sorbed on silica gel. The process could be described by pseudo-second-order kinetics. The maximum sorption capacity of PEC on the carrier was achieved at the APTES/HS ratio of 1:1. The further increase in APTES/HS ratio was accompanied by a drop of hydraulic permeability of mineral support. The immobilized PECs exhibited high efficiency in binding Pb^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions. Under dynamic conditions (PRB modeling), it was shown that the introduction of PEC into a sandy soil model significantly increased its barrier function and slowed down substantially migration of model heavy metals.

It was concluded that a new approach to immobilization of heavy metals in the contaminated aquifers was successfully tested. It is based on injection of HS/APTES complexes into sandy contaminated grounds. The optimal composition for immobilization on a mineral matrix was a mass ratio of APTES/HS = 1:1. The proposed composition could be applied for in situ installation of PRB, which is an economically effective and environmentally safe alternative to traditional methods of groundwater treatment.

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